

THEORETICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The development of an innovative economy is a complex process that requires a combination of strategic orientations, knowledge management, and organizational learning (Yu, 2013). This is further supported by the need for state regulation of innovation processes and the role of clusters, technoparks, and special economic zones in the formation of an innovative economy (Donsova, 2019). However, the institutional aspects of innovative development, such as the lack of funds, high costs, and low demand for new goods and services, can impede this process (Plisova, 2020). To address these challenges, the construction and development of innovative enterprises is crucial, with a focus on private enterprises in particular (Xu, 2021).*

Keywords: *innovations, innovative development of entrepreneurship, national economy.*

Abstrakt. *Innovatsion iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish murakkab jarayon bo'lib, strategik yo'nalishlar, bilimlarni boshqarish va tashkiliy ta'limni uyg'unlashtirishni talab qiladi (Yu, 2013). Bu innovatsion jarayonlarni davlat tomonidan tartibga solish zarurati hamda innovatsion iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishda klasterlar, texnoparklar va maxsus iqtisodiy zonalarning roli bilan yanada mustahkamlanadi (Donsova, 2019). Biroq, innovatsion rivojlanishning institutsional jihatlari, masalan, mablag'larning etishmasligi, yuqori xarajatlar va yangi tovarlar va xizmatlarga talabning pastligi bu jarayonga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin (Plisova, 2020). Ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun innovatsion korxonalarini qurish va rivojlantirish, xususan, xususiy korxonalariga e'tibor berish juda muhimdir (Xu, 2021).*

Kalit so'zlar: *innovatsiyalar, tadbirkorlikning innovatsion rivojlanishi, milliy iqtisodiyot.*

Абстракт. *Развитие инновационной экономики — сложный процесс, требующий сочетания стратегических ориентаций, управления знаниями и организационного обучения (Ю, 2013). В пользу этого говорят необходимость государственного регулирования инновационных процессов и роль кластеров, технопарков и особых экономических зон в формировании инновационной экономики (Донсова, 2019). Однако институциональные аспекты инновационного развития, такие как недостаток средств, высокие затраты и низкий спрос на новые товары и услуги, могут препятствовать этому процессу (Плисова, 2020). Для решения этих проблем решающее значение имеет строительство и развитие инновационных предприятий, особенно частных предприятий (Сюй, 2021).*

Ключевые слова: *инновации, инновационное развитие предпринимательства, национальная экономика.*

Introduction. Today, the world economy is gradually globalizing. No country in the world can escape its influence on certain spheres of public life. The process of «globalization» affects the development of innovative entrepreneurship. Today, the driving force of the functioning of innovative entrepreneurship in ensuring economic growth is its development and this is one of the

main prerequisites for the successful functioning of entrepreneurship in various sectors of the economy, an incentive to increase production efficiency. Innovative entrepreneurship is a special innovative process of creating a new, a kind of management, aimed at finding new ideas and opportunities for commercial use of innovations.

Methods. The study uses the fundamental provisions of economic theory. General scientific principles of conducting complex scientific researches were used to solve the set tasks. In the process of research a number of general scientific methods were used, in particular: analogies, logical generalization and system analysis.

Results. Innovative entrepreneurship is considered as a new way of small business development, using the achievements of modern science. The study of innovative entrepreneurship allowed to understand the modern directions of development of the market and enter new paths of economic development, in particular, highlighting the problems and prospects for its development.

As the level of economic development increases, the importance of using innovations on a large scale increases. Unfortunately, the most important competitive advantage - the level of development of science and intellectual products (patents, know-how, information) are used in our practice only in a very small amount. In almost all positions, the bulk of domestic products is clearly inferior to foreign counterparts.

Opportunities to compete both on the global and Ukrainian commodity markets were sharply limited as soon as the advantages of low resource prices and factors of extensive growth disappeared. In the Uzbekistan economy, there are still few business entities that fully engage in innovative business activities. This situation is caused by the complexity of perception and the practical transition to an innovative management system after many years of forced redistribution and concentration of resources.

In addition, resource limitations should encourage production to remove these limitations Topic Finance, Banking and Insurance through innovation. However, motivating motives can be practically suppressed, on the one hand, during economic crises and uncertainty of development, and on the other hand, when the return on invested funds is reduced. Therefore, the general state of the economy and material production affects the development of innovative entrepreneurship. It is necessary to formulate a number of principle provisions that determine the change of the economic climate in the innovation sphere (see Fig.1).

1. Increasing, in the conditions of a market economy, attention to the determination of expected future consumer requests.

2. The need to work with consumers in close contact, helping them use the proposed new product or technology to shape their business.

The commercialization of the innovation process is noticeably increasing, the pace and scale of entrepreneurial activity in this field are changing.

In contrast to the production process, the innovation process is characterized by:

- the number and uncertainty of ways to achieve the goal and high risk; - impossibility of detailed planning and orientation to forecast estimates; - the need to overcome resistance, both in the field of established economic relations and the interests of participants in the innovation process¹.

¹ Zhavoronok, A., & Marych, A. (2020). Theoretical fundamentals of innovative entrepreneurship development in the national economy. *The economic discourse*.

development of production. Today, they can earn profits much easier on some other operations not related to production. The lack of funding in full increases the time of implementation of competitive projects, reducing the quality of innovations. The solution to this problem for state-owned enterprises depends entirely on the planned allocation of the budget of Uzbekistan.

Financing of innovative projects of private enterprises mainly depends on the possibility of obtaining loan funds, which in the conditions of the crisis and taking into account the peculiarities of the domestic market of credit products forces entrepreneurs to turn to foreign credit organizations.

World practice shows that the innovation process and internal production of innovative technologies are more effective with the maximum involvement of business.

Enterprises are given not just budget money, but loans. Even for a working enterprise, bank loans, which are taken at seemingly small interest rates and for which they do not have time to pay off, are beyond their power. Therefore, the problem is very high credit rates that exist today.

Discussion. In order to solve the problems of development of innovative entrepreneurship it is necessary to: develop a legal framework that includes the definition of «innovation»; create competition that is possible only with good financial incentives; to train qualified personnel, and for this purpose the opening of innovation and technological centers at the university will be effective; develop new venture financing programs (creation of a large number of innovation and technology centers, technology parks and business incubators); organize exhibitions and product presentations in the regions. Prospects for further research into innovative entrepreneurship may be to strengthen the financial support for the development of innovative entrepreneurship by improving the fiscal policy of support for business entities.

Summary. The paper discusses the impact of globalization on innovative entrepreneurship and emphasizes the importance of developing a legal framework, creating competition with financial incentives, training qualified personnel, developing new venture financing programs, and organizing exhibitions and product presentations in the regions to solve the problems of innovative entrepreneurship. Innovative entrepreneurship is considered as a new way of small business development, utilizing the achievements of modern science.

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